

DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE WRITING SKILLS

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Over the years, English writing has experienced significant changes. It is one of the four essential language abilities alongside listening, speaking, and reading. Having good writing abilities is essential for both our personal and professional lives as well as for our academic success. Whether you're writing essays, research papers, or exams, being able to express yourself clearly and professionally can boost your credibility and provide you with opportunities for career advancement. This article's goal is to provide readers with an understanding of writing skills and the writing process. Of all the skills, writing represents the skill that needs to be learned and practiced a lot because it does not come naturally as the speaking skill, but it requires students to make special efforts in order to be learnt how to do it appropriately.

Key-words: writing skill, the product/ process approach, writing stages, writing barriers.

Introduction

Being able to write well is a form of effective communication, which many employers see as a crucial job skill. Writing represents one of the four main skills of language learning alongside speaking, listening, and reading, and it is at the heart of academic life because good writing makes good students. As Ch. Tribble says in his book on writing: *to be deprived of the opportunity to learn to write is ...to be excluded from a wide range of social roles, including those that the majority of people in industrialised societies associate with power and prestige.*” (Apud: Harmer, 2004 : 10) Teaching writing is important not only in order to develop our students' writing competence, but also to promote the acquisition of a second language they are learning. However, a great number of students sometimes experience difficulty in writing academic papers because they have not received a sufficient training in their schools and they are not aware of the correct way to organize their ideas and give a logical development of their thoughts in a meaningful form.

It is said that writing is the skill that has to be developed only after the other previous three skills have been improved. Although the majority of our learners have a good level of spoken English, a lot of them do not have a good command of the writing process. Moreover, it is not the intelligence of our learners that is not good enough; it is the training that is at fault. Nevertheless, we can face this issue through a lot of practice, exposure, and familiarizing our learners with basic rules of the writing process. Therefore, writing, like any other skill, is something we can get better at with time and practice. Before coming to classes and teaching our students what the writing process is about, it is advisable to turn our attention to some important principles related to writing skills that should be taken into account when teaching writing (Gincu, 2021 : 11-12) :

- Students learn best by *doing* (practising). Practice is the best way for students to learn. It is our responsibility to provide them with a variety of writing assignments for worthwhile goals in order to spark their interest in the assignments.
- Getting better at writing requires doing it a lot. Regular writing chances are essential for developing one's writing skills and for streamlining the writing process.
- The *purpose* and *audience* shape the entire writing process. Before requiring students to write, teachers make this clear to them.

- Writing is a process, not a ‘one-shot-act’ to produce a product for the teacher/examiner. (*Apud* : Turbill, Barton, 2015 : 8)

- Not only do we learn to write, but we also write in order to learn. Writing is a way for us to find, connect, clarify, and share our knowledge and identities.

- Writing involves four elements: the writer, the reader, the ideas, and the craft. “I (writer) intend to persuade you (reader) of the importance of X (ideas) and will do so in Y form (craft)”. (Walshe, 1980)

- *What* is being written will shape *how* and in what *form* it is finally presented.

- The continuum of writing begins with reflection and culminates in publication.

- In order to provide an example for the students, teachers should write with them and share their writing as much as they can, including what it takes to write.

- In addition to giving students plenty of real-world opportunities to share and publish their writing, teachers must assist students in understanding writing as a process. They stop being the one who assigns homework and takes the result back for editing without taking part in the writing process.

- Instructors need to keep an eye on their students’ writing and demonstrate to them how their writing is developing. Every writer needs a companion on the writing journey - someone who will support and encourage.

- Reading and writing are not binary opposites (i.e. it is false to perceive reading as passive reception and writing as active production). Students learn to read texts from a writer’s point of view and write texts from a reader’s point of view.

- In order to enhance students’ writing skills, foster a positive writing attitude, and boost their confidence, effective writing routines should be implemented when they are 7-10.

As digital literacy is vitally important for both students and teachers, in foreign language teaching we need to decide what kind of writing we expect from our learners and what kind of literacy we are asking from them. As teachers, we should focus our attention not only on the **product approach** to writing, but also on the process of writing itself. However, many educators advocate a **process approach** to writing because students have to be aware of the various stages that any piece of writing goes through. The product is the ultimate goal, but because we are interested in students’ needs, we have to focus on their linguistic proficiency to help them produce coherent, accurate and appropriate written messages inside and outside the classroom; so, we want to teach our learners writing skills, and that involves both the process writing and the result, the final product (Douglas Brown, 1994 : 320-321) :

Product vs Process

<i>PRODUCT</i>	<i>PROCESS</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>emphasis more on structures:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>grammar</i> ✓ <i>sentence structure</i> ✓ <i>spelling</i> ✓ <i>punctuation</i> ✓ <i>vocabulary</i> ✓ <i>linkers</i> • <i>content less important than mechanics</i> • <i>meet certain standards of prescribed English rhetorical style</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>focus on the process of writing that leads to the final written product;</i> • <i>help students to understand their own composing process;</i> • <i>help learners to build repertoires of strategies for prewriting, drafting, rewriting;</i> • <i>give students time to write and rewrite;</i> • <i>place central importance on the process of revision;</i> • <i>let learners discover what they want to say as they write;</i> • <i>give students feedback throughout the composing process (not just on the final product) to consider as they attempt to bring their expression closer and closer to intention;</i> • <i>encourage feedback both from the instructor and peers;</i> • <i>include individual conferences between teacher and student during the process of composition.</i>

With the *product approach*, teachers focus on what a final piece of writing will look like and measure it against criteria of vocabulary, grammatical use, spelling, and punctuation. This approach has been criticized because it focuses on imitation and it does not prepare students for the real world. In the mid-1970s, the *process approach* began to replace it. The process approach comprises four stages: 1. prewriting; 2) composing/drafting; 3) revising; and 4) editing. This approach is widely accepted because it allows students to understand the steps involved in the writing process, they can refine their viewpoints, and the various stages help them to improve their work due to different discussions, research, and interaction they may have. Thus, the writing process is recursive – the steps repeat and loop back in a non-linear progression. When teachers concentrate on genre, students study texts in the genre in which they are going to be writing before they embark on their own work. The **genre approach** became popular in 1980. This approach highlights three features of genre writing: firstly, students have to think carefully about the context they are writing for; secondly, they need to identify the audience they are writing for, and thirdly, they have to look at how typically effective examples of writing in the genre are constructed. (Harmer, 2015 : 365) By investigating different genres, students can perceive the differences in structure and form and apply what they learn to their own writing. Supporters of this approach say that students can notice how different discourses require different structures. (Gou, 2005)

Students write a variety of assignments at universities, ranging from lengthy reports and portfolios that may require a lot of time to complete, to brief essays they write for exams. A typical mistake made by students is to start writing before they are ready and get the impression that once they have completed their first draft, they are done. In fact, composing a good piece of writing requires a number of procedures. Writing does not come naturally, unlike speaking, so it is a skill that students need to learn and practice. A good writer will think about readers' needs, the genre, content, and tone, and will find the best way to order the information, as well as vocabulary, grammar, and cohesive devices. Learners might perceive writing as being “difficult” or “time-consuming”, and this is typically due to their incapacity to decide what to write about instead of the writing process itself. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure that our students either have ideas and enough input to write about or that they have the abilities and confidence to come up with ideas before asking them to produce written language. This is especially helpful for students preparing for written exams, when they will not have much time to come up with many different ideas. Penny Ur says that *the advantage of giving writing assessments in class is that you (teacher) are there to provide support and immediate feedback; you can help with vocabulary, spelling, and you have a chance to see and correct the mistakes immediately...* According to the author, teaching spelling rules, handwriting, touch-typing, and giving in-class writing activities are very important because our students do need to know the basic rules in order to be able to write correctly and these abilities make a huge difference to the fluency. (Penny, 2016 : 113-117) Thus, Douglas Brown H. (1994 : 327) enumerate the following micro skills that are essential for writing production:

- produce graphemes and orthographic patterns of English;
- produce writing at an efficient rate of speed to suit the purpose;
- produce an acceptable core of words and use appropriate word order patterns;
- use acceptable grammatical systems (e.g. tense, agreement, pluralization), patterns, and rules;
- express a particular meaning in different grammatical forms;
- use cohesive devices in written discourse;
- use the rhetorical forms and conventions of written discourse;

- appropriately accomplish the communicative functions of written texts according to form and purpose;
- convey links and connections between events and communicate such relations as main idea, supporting idea, new information, given information, generalization, and exemplification;
- distinguish between literal and implied meanings when writing;
- correctly convey culturally specific references in the context of the written text;
- develop and use a battery of writing strategies, such as accurately assessing the audience's interpretation, using pre-writing devices, writing with fluency in the first draft, using paraphrases and synonyms, soliciting peer and instructor feedback, and using feedback for revising and editing.

The instructor has to take into account the unique characteristics and issues associated with each style of writing when determining whether to incorporate into the classroom. Shortly after language learners start reading, they should be taught to write in the target language. Different genres of writing are laid out differently, different writing communities obey different punctuation and layout conventions in communications; that is why we need to be aware of these conventions and modify them when appropriate to get the message as clearly as we can. We have noticed that some of students start writing their essays without planning their work and this may result in miscommunication. Depending on the audience, we have to choose different varieties of expressions and a correct strategy because choice of wrong words, absence of punctuation marks, and poor organization of ideas can bring vagueness in the message. Different audience may perceive a message in different ways because their perception levels are not the same. The audience that students consider for their writing is usually their teachers. We must push them, nevertheless, to write for readers outside of the classroom. This can help them better understand how to adapt their content and language choices to match the rhetorical situation (writer, purpose, audience, message, context and culture). Teaching writing has to concentrate on genre and register while the teacher will:

- ✓ show students samples of different genre;
- ✓ develop distinct skills;
- ✓ explore language and build confidence;
- ✓ allow collaboration and peer teaching;
- ✓ teach specific writing tasks (formal/informal letter; discursive writing; story writing);
- ✓ encourage committed reading (of the well-written tasks that were mentioned above) and model student writing (on such tasks);
- ✓ teach different grammars (formal, informal) using formal/informal comparisons;
- ✓ teach register chunks for different genres (phrases for opening a letter; ways of developing a story; structures to use in reports...). (Turula, 2010 : 377)

A student can learn to become a good writer by: a) being actively encouraged and helped to follow through a series of preparatory steps before the final text is produced, and b) becoming more aware of the preparation process, so that it can be done more independently in future. (Scrivener, 2005 : 194) We should use a wide variety of writing, strategies, each suited to particular objectives and requirements. This is crucial for maintaining interest because students become bored if they are asked to complete the same kind of task repeatedly. Unless the learners are given opportunities to write what they want to write, they will never learn this skill. English writing encompasses various types (narrative writing, descriptive writing, expository writing, persuasive writing, technical writing...), each serving distinct purposes and learners should be aware of them:

Types of Writing

<p>A.Vizental (2008)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • functional writing: memos, advertisements, application forms, letters of complaint, CVs. This type of writing refers to writing tasks that have a specific purpose behind their production. Therefore, teachers should be aware of the importance of endowing their students with consistent functional writing skills. Teaching functional writing should vary according to the age interests of the students • academic writing: compositions, essays, research papers, reports, encyclopedia entries. Compared to functional style, it is more mentally demanding and has a far more intricate structure. Academic writing's complex structure is one of its key characteristics, demanding a great deal of skill and effort to produce. • creative writing: diaries, informal letters, articles, stories, poems. Writing that is creative is expressive and handles the writer's thoughts and emotions in a creative and artful fashion. For optimal outcomes, educators must provide students with examples of many written discourses and closely highlight the distinctive elements of each one, such as format and structure, writing styles, etc. (p. 246-247)
<p>H.Douglas Brown (1994)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • imitative writing/writing down: in this writing beginner students start writing by copying materials that they have already mastered by hearing, speaking and reading in order to learn the conventions of the orthographic code. The materials may be the texts that they have memorized. Since in this writing language learners only “imitate”, they write groups of words, sentences or phrases rather than single words. Some forms of dictation fall into this category, even though A. Bambang Setiyadi takes dictation as another type of writing. By having dictation, language learners practice having aural comprehension and spelling correctly. • controlled /intensive writing: it is similar to rewriting, but in this writing language learners change a passage from dialogue to narrative or vice versa. Controlled writing may take a form of letter. This step may be given to more advanced learners after they have been given considerable practice in controlled writing. The practice in controlled writing can guide language learners to have composition in the target language. Another form of controlled writing is to take a paragraph and change all present tense verbs to past. In a dicto-comp, the paragraph is read at normal speed and the teacher puts the key words from the paragraph in sequence and asks students to rewrite it from their recollection of the reading, using the given words. • self-writing: notetaking is a proper example, when students may take notes during a lecture for the purpose of later recall. Dialogue journal helps students to write their thoughts, feelings and reactions in a journal and the instructor reads and responds. • display writing: short answer exercises, essay examinations, and even research reports involve this type of writing. For students, one of the academic skills that they need to master is the variety of display writing techniques. • real writing has three subcategories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ academic: The Language Experience Approach gives groups of students opportunities to convey genuine information to each other. Content based instruction encourages the exchange of useful information, and some of it uses the written word; group problem-solving tasks may have a writing component in which information is sought and conveyed; peer-editing work adds to what would otherwise be an audience of one (instructor) and provides real writing opportunity. ➤ technical/vocational: a variety of real writing can take place in classes of students studying English for advancement in their occupation: letters, directions for some operation or assembly might be given, actual forms can be filled out. ➤ personal: diaries, letters, notes, post cards and other informal writing can take place. While certain tasks may be contrived, nevertheless the genuine exchange of information can happen (p.327-330)

In fact, teachers give credit for successful task achievement and for accuracy, content, register, and cohesion, the way things are ordered and joined together because a good piece of writing is carefully constructed and all the parts are properly linked, not just put next to each other; phrases are connected to form sentences, sentences are joined to make paragraphs, and paragraphs are linked to build a text. The ability to use the right style/register is one of the skills that should be mastered at the very beginning of the writing process because this can cause unintentionally comic results. Although there are many degrees of formality, most written English is situated between formal and informal register. Malcom Mann et al. (2003 : 111) list some of the most characteristic features that differentiate formal and informal English:

Formal/Informal style

<i>A more formal style is appropriate for:</i>	<i>A more informal style is appropriate for:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a discursive composition for a teacher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an article for your school magazine
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a report for a manager / employer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a letter to a friend
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a letter to somebody you do not know personally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • direct speech in a story
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a story, apart from direct speech 	
<i>Formal writing examples:</i>	<i>Informal writing examples:</i>
no contractions <i>I do not think there is any excuse for the treatment I received.</i>	contractions <i>There's something else I've got to tell you.</i>
formal set phrases <i>I look forward to hearing from you.</i>	informal set phrases <i>Thanks for your letter.</i>
formal greetings in letters <i>Dear Sir/Madam, Dear Mr/Mrs...</i>	informal greetings in letters <i>Dear Ann,</i>
inversions <i>Seldom have I had a worse meal.</i>	incomplete sentences <i>Great news about your brother.</i>
complete sentences <i>In my view, we should consider redoing the shop window display.</i>	informal vocabulary, including phrasal verbs <i>'go on' instead of 'continue'</i>
formal vocabulary, usually not using phrasal verbs <i>'tolerate' instead of 'put up with'</i>	direct questions <i>How was your holiday last month?</i>
indirect questions <i>I wonder if you could inform me about the cost of the course.</i>	more use of the active voice <i>They've built a new cinema near our house.</i>
more use of the passive voice <i>The majority of local sports centres were opened in the last ten years.</i>	informal connecting words and phrases <i>Well, I think that's about all I wanted to say.</i>
formal connecting words and phrases <i>In addition to this, many people feel that the police are underfunded.</i>	simpler sentence structure <i>I'll be late for the party. It's because of my French exam.</i>

<p>more complex sentence structure <i>Knowing what a good reputation the restaurant has, I was disappointed with the service.</i></p>	<p>punctuation using exclamation marks <i>if you'd been at the wedding, you'd have loved the food!</i></p>
<p>punctuation using semi-colons <i>The library offers no facilities for borrowing videos; this is because of the high cost involved.</i></p>	

P. Gurrey identifies four main issues with writing progress that need to be addressed: *inadequate preparation for the writing; having to write without purpose or objective; lack of help that shows exactly how to improve the writing; unsuitable subjects to write about.* (1961 : 129) So, when planning to write, students need to consider what the purpose of their writing is, the audience, and the content structure. In the context of education, it is important to keep in mind that most exams, whether they are assessing a student's proficiency in a foreign language or other skills, examiners typically use students' writing skills to gauge their level of knowledge. That is why the type of writing teachers get their students to do will depend on their age, level, and interests (elementary students - postcards, intermediate students – articles, newspaper headlines, and advanced students – reports...). If we want our students to get good results, we have to make sure that they possess enough language input on the given topic. The role of input is undeniably crucial. The choice of a subject needs to be given especially careful thought. Both language and subject-matter challenges should be avoided by students since the goal is to improve their proficiency with the language they have already learned, not to search for new words or make mistakes when attempting to convey topics they do not fully understand. To help students learn how to use the language with ease and confidence, we must select subjects that are relevant to their everyday lives and ones they are at ease to discuss. Thus, they will be able to concentrate on using correct language and well-constructed phrases and their ideas will flow freely, with less confusion. The ideal subjects are the ones that are practical and concrete; we should guide clear topics or notions that cause linguistic challenges and focus on helping students develop both their cognitive and metacognitive understanding, as these are key factors in determining how well their writing turns out. A useful way to improve their English writing skills is to know how to write a paragraph and what a paragraph consists of:

- ✓ an indented first line;
- ✓ a *topic sentence* that gives the main idea; if the paragraph does not have a topic sentence, the reader may be confused because the organization of ideas will be not clear;
- ✓ a body of sentences all about the main idea; these sentences make up the body of the paragraph and are called *supporting sentences*. They give more information about the topic, such as details, examples, or reasons; these supporting sentences should not include ideas that are unrelated or unconnected to the topic;
- ✓ a *concluding sentence* that ends the paragraph with a final thought, expresses the same idea as the topic sentence using different words and does not give any new information about the topic. (Keith, Folse, 2020 : 30-48)

The academic writing process typically involves several stages that are essential for producing a well-structured, well-researched, and well-written paper (*Ibidem* : 28-38) :

➤ *Pre-writing*: this is the initial planning phase where you choose a topic, gather research materials, and develop your ideas. The choice of the topic should not be too general or too specific. The purpose of this stage is to activate students' background knowledge, which is essential for them

to understand the topic. Teachers can ask leading questions or provide students with information by using aids such as pictures, slides, film excerpts... Brainstorming, clustering, listing, outlining, freewriting, looping, asking questions are all strategies of pre-writing.

➤ *Research*: conduct in-depth research to collect information and sources relevant to your topic. This may involve reading and data collection.

➤ *Brainstorm*: there are several good ideas to organize your ideas (mind maps, completing a Venn diagram, or drawing a T-chart). Select the ideas that you can use to write a well-developed essay.

➤ *Thesis statement*: it is very important to know how to develop a clear thesis statement that outlines the main argument or point of the paper. It tells the reader what the essay is about and why it is written. The thesis statement contains the *controlling idea* (a word, phrase, clause that states the writer's opinion). With the topic and controlling idea, a thesis statement provides a blueprint for the organization of the essay.

➤ *Outline*: create a structured outline to organize your ideas. It helps to see which areas of the essay are strong/weak. When organizing the outline, we should determine the logical sequence of the ideas and the way to move from one paragraph to another. The simplest form comprises simply adding numbers/or letters to ideas generated during brainstorming. An outline has three features: parallel structure (each heading and subheading should have the same form), coordination (each heading should have equal significance), and subordination (headings should be more general, while subheadings should be more specific).

➤ *Drafting*: write the first draft of the paper. Focus on getting your ideas down on paper without worrying too much about perfection at this stage because this can cause you to lose some of your ideas. After writing it, one of the most effective strategies is to set your essay aside for a few hours. When rereading it, we may find several places where we want to change words/ideas.

➤ *Get feedback from a peer*: ask someone to look at your ideas. Peer editing is used for the first draft, but it can also be useful for hooks and outlines. This is an important step towards the final goal of a polished essay because your colleagues may notice things that we missed.

➤ *Revision*: it is about the opportunity you have to rethink (re-vision) or revise your draft for clarity, coherence, and organization. Once you have received comments from a peer, use feedback to improve the essay. Make sure your arguments are well-supported and your writing is concise. Experts from University of Maryland Baltimore County come with a great tip that is of a great help, and namely TRIP:

❖ topic: the reader easily understands the topic and the main points of each paragraph and sentence.

❖ relate: the reader can easily follow the discussion and how each idea relates to another.

❖ important: the reader can tell what ideas are most important.

❖ precise: the reader understands the exact meaning of your ideas.

➤ *Editing*: this stage is when you check your paper for grammar, spelling, capitalization, punctuation and sometimes, word choice after you have improved the content and organization of the text. Ensure that your paper adheres to all the requirements that have been given to you. Having reviewed your first draft, you can shape it as the final version of your work by including all the alterations, modifications, and changes you thought of while reviewing your first draft.

➤ *Proofreading*: carefully proofread your paper for any types of errors you haven't noticed. It is often helpful to have someone else (peer or colleague) review your work as well because they may come up with some suggestions/ideas.

➤ *Final draft*: prepare the final version of your paper, incorporating all revisions and corrections.

We can support the writing process and help with effective feedback by providing models. Anticipating mistakes and errors that students are likely to make, diagnosing them when they happen, and then providing a constructive feedback will encourage them to keep going. Some general guidelines for feedback are to understand why the error has happened. For example, it was a guess, it was a careless mistake, or it showed an error in their understanding of the rules or use of language. Whenever possible, we need to use feedback mechanisms so that the students can self-edit and self-correct with a peer or in groups; we should use positive feedback over negative because learners are more likely to engage with the language when they feel motivated, and confident. Educators from University of Maryland bring some constructive feedback and error correction techniques: label all errors using specific grammatical terms or error correction codes (agreement problem, comma splice...), circle all errors (to help students label errors on their own), correct or rewriting a phrase or sentence (to model a correction or style), label an error the first or second time it occurs, instruct the student to self-correct remaining errors of that kind, look for patterns of error, and noting the two or three most common patterns in the summary comments, ask clarifying questions to help them think more deeply about their writing, and identify the writer's stem goths. Error correction is recommended in order to build students' confidence and to build their autonomy. There are mainly two types of errors that students may make: 1) *low-gravity errors* (micro issues), such as incorrect plural form, wrong preposition, missing an article. These mistakes are considered to be minor and they do not affect the meaning, 2) *high-gravity errors* (macro issues) that are serious because they carry meaning in a sentence and may interfere with comprehension. There is a lot of research evidence that error correction helps learning in both speech and writing. *What we want the students to remember is the correct form, not the mistake; so it's a good idea either to get them to self-correct, or to ask them to repeat/rewrite the correct version.* (Penny, 2016 : 23) After identifying our students' mistakes, it is worth writing a comment at the end of the piece of written work by using some interesting expressions and even give suggestions on areas that need to be improved: *I find the content..., I like the part on..., my immediate reactions to this piece of writing are..., the part on...could be further developed, you tend to ..., I'm not sure about..., the specific language errors that I have noticed are ..., the best part of this writing is...* (Harmer, 2004 :116)

P-Q-P Peer Feedback: the *praise-question-polish* is an interesting way to provide constructive peer feedback to each other. *Praise*: you can tell about one or two specific things you like about the writing; explain why you like it, and even offer specific examples from that piece of writing. *Question*: ask for more information about something specific in the writing, ask for clarification on the topic that wasn't explained well enough for you to understand it, ask why your colleague made the choice to write certain ideas. *Polish*: suggest a specific way to improve the writing, explain why you think your suggestions will improve the writing. When you peer edit a classmate's writing, choose your words carefully and make sure that:

- your comments are helpful and try to be specific about the mistakes.
- your comments are polite and say things the way you would want someone to tell you.

Peer editing can help you strengthen any areas that are weak or that appear confusing to the reader. It is important for you to understand why a piece of writing is good or bad, and the best way to do this is to read books, newspapers, and other texts as often as you can. The more writing styles you become familiar with, the better your writing will be. (Keith, Folse et al., 2020 : 22)

Conclusions: Longer, more formal written assignments don't seem to be as necessary as they formerly were, and this is evident in many schools where writing assignments are less common than those for other skills. Writing takes much more time than the other three skills of listening, reading, and speaking. It is a complex set of skills that requires continuous practice. The process of writing is produced in many different formats due to its wide range of functions: i.e. stating a point of view, synthesizing information and reporting on something, applying for a job, making a request, writing a letter and so on, that is why we use them so that they become deeply ingrained in their language habits. We should teach our students that every piece of writing needs to be planned before starting to write it on a piece of paper. Students tend to write in the way they were taught in their first language, using different registers depending on the topics they are given. It is therefore our responsibility to explain to them how the process of writing works in English. Like many other skills, one of the best ways to improve our writing is to practice it. Thus, the art of conciseness, completeness, and clarity of the message becomes an important part in our writing skills. Writing well requires research, planning, concept development, originality, and editing. All texts can be analyzed in terms of their organization and all genres have relatively strict formulae governing their construction. So, if we want our writing to be truly accessible, it also needs to be both cohesive (both lexical and grammatical cohesion) and coherent (the way in which a student sequences information). Students must acquire a range of strategies that aid in their comprehension and approach of writing assignments in order to address them successfully.

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